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Applicable & Reference documents.

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

FITS	Flexible Image Transport System
IDL	Interactive Data Language
SED	Spectral Energy Distribution
VLKB	ViaLactea Knowledge Base
LUT	LookUp Table
VisIVO	Visual Interface with the Virtual Observatory
TAP	Table Access Protocol
VO	Virtual Observatory
VTK	Visualization Toolkit
RDB	Relational DataBase
FITS	Flexible Image Transport System
Project	The VIALACTEA Project
Service	The Search & cutout service

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1. Introduction

A 3D-aided visual analytics environment allows the astronomers to easily conduct research activities using virtual reality methods for multidimensional data and information visualization. It provides real-time data interaction to carry out complex tasks for multi-criteria data/metadata queries on subsamples selection and further analysis, or real-time control of data fitting to theoretical models.

The VIALACTEA visual analytics environment is implemented as a client-server application where all data, models, analysis tools, data-mining/machine-learning tools and information is enclosed in a standardised, homogeneous and interoperable framework handled via a Science Gateway.

The Client, based on VisIVO¹ backbone, offers a 2D and 3D visual analytics environment allowing the astronomers to easily conduct research activities interacting in a simple way with the Vialactea Knowledge base and the *Search&cutout* service.

This document is the explanatory supplement of the 3D Visual Analytic client.

The version 2 of the software is the deliverable 5.4 (D5.4) of the Work Package WP5 of the VIALACTEA project.

The D5.4 delivery package is constituted of:

- The 3D Visual Analytics Version 2 software source code (visualanalytics_v2.tgz archive); due to the file size, the code is available on the VIALACTEA Wiki under the page “Deliverables”, section “WP5” subsection “D5.4”.
- The software explanatory supplement information (i.e. this document)

2. 3D Visual Analytics frontend module architecture

2.1. Software dependencies

The 3D visual analytics client is a cross-platform application that consists of a set C++ classes for the core functionalities using Qt² for the user interface. The adopted rendering engine is the Visualization Toolkit³, an open-source, freely available software system for 3D computer graphics, image processing, and visualization that supports a wide variety of visualization algorithms. To read data files in FITS (Flexible Image Transport System) data format CFITSIO⁴ library is used.

¹ <http://visivo.oact.inaf.it/>

² <https://www.qt.io/>

³ <http://www.vtk.org/>

⁴ <http://heasarc.gsfc.nasa.gov/fitsio/fitsio.html>

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2.2. 3D Visual Analytics architecture design

According to the Architecture design document [AD2], the development of the application follows the architecture depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Architecture design of the 3D Visual Analytics module

The visual analytics framework is designed employing a client – server approach.

In the client there are three macro blocks detailed as follows:

- Rendering;
- Object server: enable the visualisation clients to display data without penalising user interactivity. It offloads computations from the client-side to the server (albeit generically important, this is especially important for web-based visualisations and for visualisation in low power devices). It also lowers the need of data transfers from the server to the clients, and thus bandwidth requirements on the server (and client) side;
- Data mining algorithm interface.

Through the usage of gUSE's remote API it's possible to execute workflows on different DCI.

The access to the knowledge base DB is possible through SQL and TAP Queries. This enables the application also to access the VO catalogues.

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3. Visual Analytic Front-end v2

3.1. Visual Query

A selection of the region of interest has been developed and it is used as starting screen of the visual analytics client, in order to allow the users to easily query and retrieve from the search&cutout service [AD1] (fig.1).

Figure 1. Visual query services user interface

The image shown within the window, provided by IAPS, is a tiff image that cover the galactic plane from -60° to $+60^\circ$ in longitude and from -1° to $+1^\circ$ in latitude.

The *visual query* uses smaller tiles created using GDAL2Tiles⁵. This utility generates small tiles and a simple web page with viewer based on OpenLayers⁶ framework.

This web based approach (files are locally stored and embedded in visual analytic client) allows the user to comfortably explore, with zoom and pan functionality, galactic plane maps. Moreover, that this is also useful for dissemination purposes (e.g. on the project website).

The selection of the region of interest can be carried out choosing a point on the map and specifying the radius of selection or selecting a rectangular region. The maximum radius accepted by the *Search&Cutout* services is 2 degrees while the maximum sides [dl,db] is 1 degrees.

When queried, the *service* returns a fits image containing the user selected region (at the selected Hi-GAL band) that is used as starting point for visual analytics operations.

⁵ <http://www.gdal.org/gdal2tiles.html>

⁶ <http://openlayers.org>

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If the user checks “Save to disk” option, the image is saved locally for future uses of it, and then it can be re-loaded by clicking on the “Local Image” button.

The “Local DC” button allows the user to load and visualize a *velocity datacube* FITS file that is already stored on a local disk.

The “Select” button, under the 3D section allows the user to specify the range of coordinates on which to perform a 3D visualization of sources on the galactic plane.

3.2.2D maps visualisation

Once the selected region has been downloaded or locally loaded from the visual query Window, the 2D maps visualization window is shown. The user can interact with the displayed image changing the palette used to map pixel values with colours. There are a set of predefined LUT embedded in the Client, for each of them is possible to select if use linear or logarithmic scale.

The image can be zoomed with mouse wheel and panned dragging it when the SHIFT button is pressed.

Contrast and saturation of the visualized image can be changed by keeping pressed the mouse left button and moving on the image. Passing the mouse over the image allows to display on the bottom of the window the pixel value, and coordinates expressed as pixel (X, Y), galactic (GLON, GLAT), fk5 (RA, DEC) and ecliptic (RA, DEC).

If the visualized map is downloaded from the *Search&Cutout* service, on the right panel a list of 2D maps and datacube available in the Vialactea knowledge base within the selected region are shown (following referred as VLKB items). In order to have an idea of the region covered by each of these elements a footprint is visualized if the users click on one of this item (figure 3).

Furthermore, the user can interact with the image performing the following operations:

- Add an image as layer (see section 3.3)
- Compact sources visualization and analysis (see Section 3.4)
- Visualization of Filaments (see Section 3.5)
- Visualization of Datacubes (see Section 3.6)
- 3D Visualization (see Section 3.7)

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Figure 3: Visualization of the footprint of selected item

3.3. Add an image as layer

Double clicking on one of the VLKB items, if it is a 2D map image, it is added as new layer on top of the FITS images already displayed. The new layers are aligned (position, scaling pixel size, rotation) to the “image base” according to the information contained into their header.

Each layer is shown in the table (following referred as Layer items) in the bottom part of right panel. Using the checkbox on the left of each row within the Layer items, the user can activate or deactivate the visualisation of the relative layer. The opacity can be modified selecting a row in the Layer items and using the slider in the “Layer setting” located in the upper part of the window.

3.4. Compact sources visualization

The user can display compact sources overlapped to the fits image.

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If the user decides to retrieve compact sources dataset from the VLKB he/she should click on the “Compact Source” button (or use the shortcut cmd ⌘ +R on OsX system or ctrl+R on Linux) and make a rectangular selection of the region of interest on the visualized image. The tool, extracting coordinates from the selection made by the user, queries the VLKB (see fig. 4) and automatically displays the compact sources on top of the image on which the user is doing the analytic operations (see fig.5). By default, the client queries the VLKB in order to obtain sources from bandmerged table. If the user wants to download and visualize the compact sources of just one band, he/she can select the desired one from a dropdown list “Table” in the panel as show in figure 5.

Figure 6. Visualization of compact sources from the VLKB

The compact sources are shown in different colours on the image depending on the relative wavelength (70 μm , 160 μm , 250 μm , 350 μm and 500 μm). As for the layers, using the checkbox in Layer element the user can select/de-select the compact sources to display. Double clicking on the coloured cell of each row, it is possible to change the colour of the sources in the visualization.

3.4.1. SED Analysis

From the menu bar going to Window \rightarrow Select, or pressing the keyboard shortcut cmd ⌘ +S on OsX system or ctrl+S on Linux, the user can select one or more of the visualized clumps to perform the SED analysis.

There are three different kind of fitting operations available, one for the fit with the theoretical models and two for the analytical fit. Fitting operations are performed from the menu bar selecting Action \rightarrow Fit and then “Theoretical model” or “Grey-body” to perform the fit with the theoretical models or the analytical fits.

Fit operations are performed through the use of IDL⁷ routines integrated, in a transparent way for the user, within the client of the visual analytics tool.

Figure 7. SED plot: in blue the theoretical fit performed on the selected SED

In the right panel the user can visualize the output log or the results of the computed SED fit. A list of SED appears once a new fit is performed so that the user can select/deselect the SED fit to visualize or press the “Clear All” button to remove all the plotted fits.

If the “Select” visualization mode is selected, the user can perform the fit only on the selected nodes on the graph.

In case the SED presents multiple associations the user can choose to sum the fluxes of counterparts obtaining the SED with a cumulative flux. This operation is done by checking “Collapse All” from the right panel. In figure 8 the SED drawn in red line is the collapsed one while the dashed lines are the original SEDs.

Figure 8. SED plot: in blue the theoretical SED that fit the collapsed one drawn in red

⁷ <http://www.exelisvis.com/ProductsServices/IDL.aspx>

3.5. Filaments Visualization

Starting from the selected region, the filaments candidates stored within the VLKB, can be visualized by selecting the “Filaments” button on top of the window and making a rectangular selection. The filaments are displayed on top of the image as shown in fig. 8. The filaments are visualized with contour and spine.

Using the checkbox in “Layer items” the user can visualize or remove the filaments from visualization. Double clicking the coloured cell it is possible to change the colour of the filaments.

Figure 9. Filaments visualization

3.6. Datacube visualization

Selecting a radiocube from “VLKB items” on the visualization window (see fig. 3), the user can query the Search&Cutout service in order to get and visualize the datacube (see fig. 10).

The 3D datacube visualization (left panel) can be controlled by the mouse movements and pre-defined views (e.g. front, back or top) can be selected by the Camera Control buttons on the top panel of the window.

The 3D visualization can be zoomed with mouse wheel and panned dragging it when SHIFT button if pressed.

The 3D visualization of the datacube (see fig. 10) is rendered using isosurfaces algorithm with thresholds that the user can change in real-time using the slider “Threshold” located in the top panel.

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Figure 10. 3D datacube visualization

The right panel shows a single slice of the velocity datacube. With the “Cutting Plane” slider, the user can select which slice to visualize.

Contrast and saturation of the visualized slice can be changed by keeping pressed the mouse left button and moving on the image. Passing the mouse over the image allows to display on the bottom of the window the pixel value, and coordinates expressed as pixel (X, Y), galactic (GLON, GLAT), fk5 (RA, DEC) and ecliptic (RA, DEC).

If the checkbox in “Contours” is checked then the isocontours are displayed on top of the selected slice as shown in fig. 11. The contours are also reported on the 2D map image. Contours can be changed by selecting the “Level” and the Upper and Lower bound.

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Figure 11. Contours display on the 3D datacube visualization

3.7.3D Visualization for sources on galactic plane

The user can select a region of interest within the FITS image in order to query the VLKB obtaining a 3D visualization of compact sources on the galactic plane in that region (see fig. 11). Alternatively, the 3D visualization can be performed by clicking on the 3D button of the Starting window (see fig. 2) and then choosing the longitude and latitude min – max bounds (in degrees) of the region of interest.

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Figure 12. 3D Visualization of sources on galactic plane

The 3D view is interactive and the camera position can be moved with mouse operations. The Lut colormap scalar and type can be changed by selecting the corresponding checkbox and can be visualized in linear or logarithmic form.

If the number of visualized points is less than 1000 then the glyphs can be visualized on top of the points scaled according to the selected field.